

Analytical performance of host elements measurement in neodymium doped phosphate laser glasses using ICP-AES

P. K. Sinha*, S. Mandal, R. Samaddar and D. Kundu

Analytical Chemistry Section, Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, 196, Raja S. C. Mullick Road, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : psinha@cgcri.res.in

Manuscript received online 30 August 2012, revised 18 February 2013, accepted 11 March 2013

Abstract : A simple and reliable analytical method was developed using inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) for rapid simultaneous determination of aluminium, barium and potassium as host materials in neodymium doped phosphate laser glass. The method has been developed by checking the spectral interferences for the optimal line selection including determination of linearity and selectivity. The sensitivity was investigated using calibration curves obtained in presence of the matrix. Accuracy and precision of the proposed method was studied by the analysis of standard reference materials of different glass matrices and spiked in sample solution. The obtained recoveries and %RSD of those analytes were very satisfactory and as well as having no significant matrix effect. The developed method can be applied for routine analysis of phosphate laser glasses.

Keywords : ICP-AES, phosphate laser glass, host elements.

Introduction

Increased interest in phosphate-based laser glass has been noted in the last two decades both among the users of laser technology and among its developers. All the leading optical firms involved in the production of laser glass are currently fabricating active elements from phosphate glasses¹⁻³. Furthermore, phosphate glasses are important from the viewpoint of practical industrial applications, because the glass can possess a lower glass transition temperature (T_g) than conventional silicate and borate glasses. Among them potassium-barium-aluminium-phosphate based glass have a high cross section for stimulated emission, low nonlinear refractive index, and good thermal characteristics^{4,5}. To maintain the quality of such speciality glass, accurate determination of host elements as well as trace impurities are very important. Among the modern analytical instruments ICP-AES is mostly used technique for the simultaneous determination of multi elements over a wide concentration range with very low detection limit at several spectral lines⁶⁻⁸.

The main objective of this present study was to develop an analytical method for direct and simultaneous measurement of Al_2O_3 , BaO and K_2O as host materials in

neodymium doped phosphate laser glass using ICP-AES. The sensitivity of the method with respect to each analyte was studied using the slope of the calibration curves. For estimation of precision and accuracy of the method, each element at different concentrations spiked in the phosphate laser glass sample and as well as different standard reference materials of glasses were analyzed. The developed method has been successfully applied for routine analysis of phosphate laser glass samples.

Experimental

Reagents and standards :

The following reagents and standards were employed. Nitric acid ultra pure, concentration (65% w/v), Merck, ICP Standard stock solutions (1000 mg/L) of aluminium, barium and potassium of Merck, Germany for preparation of multi elements calibration standard. The concentration of multi elements standard of Al, Ba and K in the range (10–30 mg/L), were prepared in nitric acid 5% (v/v) solution with addition of 60 mg/L standard P_2O_5 solution in each working standard for matrix matching. The concentration of P_2O_5 in working standard is 60 mg/L because in glass sample solution after dilution contains nearly

50–60 mg/L P_2O_5 . Three calibration standards were prepared by serial dilution of the primary stock solution maintaining nitric acid 5% (v/v) concentration. Deionised double distilled water used through out the experiment.

Instrumentation :

All experiments were performed using Spectro Ciros Vision direct-reading ICP-AES (model Spectro Ciros Vision, Spectro GmbH, Germany) in this study. This instrument equipped with a solid state CCD detector allow simultaneous monitoring of all the analytical lines, and an optimized optical design gives excellent signal-to-noise performance, resulting in low detection limits. Analysis was based on peak area measurement since the chemical matrix interference, normally observed during ICP-AES measurements with use of peak height were greatly reduced in peak area measurement. Good signal-background ratio was also obtained on peak area measurement. The instrumentation and operating conditions are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Specification of the spectrometer, ICP source and operating conditions

Spectrometer	Spectro Ciros Vission
View	Radial view
Optical system	Holographic
Wavelength range (nm)	120–770
Detector	High performance solid state detector
RF frequency (MHz)	27.12
Coolant gas flow ($L\ min^{-1}$)	12.0
Nebulizer	Cross flow
Plasma torch	Standard quartz torch
Pump	Peristaltic
Incident power (W)	1200
Nebulizer gas flow rate ($L\ min^{-1}$)	0.9
Auxiliary gas flow ($L\ min^{-1}$)	1
Read time (s)	60
Delay time (s)	40
Optical resolution (nm)	0.009

Sample preparation :

Weigh accurately about 0.2 g of different phosphate glass samples (–200 mesh and oven dried at 105 °C for 2 h) and taken in PTFE (poly tetra fluoro ethylene) basin. The sample was digested by adding a mixture of 5 ml HF ultra pure, concentrating (48% w/v) and 5 ml HNO_3 ultra

pure, concentrating (65% w/v) on sand bath at (140 ± 10) °C. The process was repeated till complete dissolution of the sample. The residual mass was dissolved in HNO_3 5% (v/v) and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. Similarly a blank solution was prepared.

Results and discussion

Selection of spectral line :

In Table 2, three spectral lines of each analyte, except potassium (only two spectral lines are available in instrument software) together with the results of background equivalent concentration (BEC), detection limit (DL), correlation coefficient (r), slope and intercept are presented. The BEC is expressed as the analyte concentration that produces a net signal (peak minus background) equal to the background. That is, an analyte concentra-

Table 2. Result of calibration curve of the method and related data : a = slope, b = intercept

Analyte spectral line	BEC (mg/L)	DL (mg/L)	Co. coef. (r)	$Y = ax + b$
Al 394.401	0.790	0.0143	0.99997	$1.42x + 0.31$
Al 396.152	0.435	0.0244	0.99999	$3.29x + 0.16$
Al 309.271	0.924	0.0664	0.99999	$2.3x + 0.22$
Ba 233.527	0.135	0.0045	0.99991	$0.243x + 0.04$
Ba 455.404	0.0228	0.0019	0.99999	$7.74x + 0.32$
Ba 230.426	0.139	0.00492	0.99999	$0.19x + 0.02$
K 766.491	1.15	0.0887	0.99996	$1.29x + 0.33$
K 404.72	434	1.21	0.84933	$0.16x + 10.31$

tion for which the signal-to-background ratio is one. The lower BEC indicates greater sensitivity. DL is expressed as the practical limit of quantification which is determined by three times of the standard deviation of the blank. The correlation coefficient (r) and slope are considered as sensitivity of the method and the value of intercept is indicated that the calibration curve passes close to origin. Optimization of other important parameters like nebulizer argon gas flow, sample uptake flow and RF power were already done and reported in our previous paper⁹. The best spectral line of each analyte was selected on the basis of lower BEC and DL, higher slope, $r > 0.9$ and lower intercepts value (lower the intercept value, better the calibration curve). The selected spectral line of aluminium, barium and potassium were found to be 396.152 nm, 455.404 nm and 766.491 nm respec-

tively which were used through out the study.

Preparation of calibration standards :

Multi element standard solutions were prepared containing 30 mg/L of barium, potassium and aluminium, in 5% HNO₃ solution. Phosphate standard of 60 mg/L was taken here for matrix matching because it present in laser glass sample (around 60%, w/w). Similarly a blank solution was also prepared using same acid concentration. The prepared multi element standard solution was diluted appropriately stepwise to prepare other working calibration standards maintaining same acid concentration. The range of the calibration curve was selected to match the expected concentration of investigated elements in phosphate laser glass sample. Calibration curve of three analytes at selected wavelengths is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Calibration curve of three analytes at selected wavelength.

Precision and accuracy :

In order to assess the accuracy and precision of the proposed method generally standard reference materials are analyzed using proposed method. Since phosphate laser glass is a new type of specialty glass, so standard

reference material (SRM) of same matrix is not available so far. Therefore the accuracy and precision of the proposed method for the determination of the analytes (Al, Ba and K) were evaluated by spiking known concentration of analytes in neodymium doped phosphate laser glass sample No. 2. This phosphate laser glass sample was analysed for Al, Ba and K five times and their mean values of those analytes were considered as reference values. The % recovery and % RSD of aluminium, barium, potassium (97.2 to 101.0), (97.3 to 101.2), (97.5 to 101.9) and (0.77 to 2.04), (0.95 to 2.10), (0.92 to 2.13) were found and shown in Table 3, which indicate that proposed method is precise and accurate. Again an attempt was taken to validate the proposed method by analyzing standard reference materials of different glasses having no matching matrix of phosphate laser glass. It was found the results of analytes were good agreement with the certified value and also interference of matrix effect was not found so far, as shown in Table 4. The developed method was used successfully in routine analysis of neodymium doped phosphate laser glass, given in Table 5.

Analysis of phosphate glass samples :

Samples of different batch of neodymium doped phosphate glass were decomposed by the process mentioned in the experimental part. After selecting the proper wavelength of three analytes, samples were measured by ICP-AES at optimum measuring condition. A set of five replica of all the samples were measured. The final concentrations of analytes (mg/kg) were calculated relative to the initial sample mass. The result of mean concentration in mg/kg and their standard deviation are given in Table 5. The standard deviation presented in the table was calculated from the measured value in mg/kg of 5 replica. It

Table 3. Analytical results of Al, Ba and K spiked in phosphate laser glass sample No. 2, n=5
(Reference values : Al 6.53 mg/L, Ba 12.30 mg/L and K 11.52 mg/L)

Added analytes (mg/L)	Total quantity, reference value + added value (mg/L)			Quantity found (mg/L)			% of recovery			% RSD		
	Al	Ba	K	Al	Ba	K	Al	Ba	K	Al	Ba	K
20.00	26.53	32.30	31.52	26.80	31.87	31.88	101.0	98.7	101.1	1.82	1.70	2.13
15.00	21.53	27.30	26.52	21.21	27.53	25.86	98.5	100.8	97.5	2.02	1.04	1.34
10.00	16.53	22.30	21.52	16.25	21.81	21.93	98.3	97.8	101.9	0.94	1.01	0.96
5.00	11.53	17.30	16.52	11.63	16.84	16.24	100.9	97.3	98.3	0.77	0.84	1.02
1.00	7.53	13.30	12.52	7.32	13.48	12.71	97.2	101.2	101.5	0.79	0.91	0.94

Table 4. Analytical results of different standard reference materials of glass using proposed method

Name of standard/sample	%Element oxide (certified value)			Observed value (w/w%) \pm SD ^a		
	Al ₂ O ₃	BaO	K ₂ O	Al ₂ O ₃	BaO	K ₂ O
NIST SRM 89	0.18	1.40	8.40	0.17 \pm 0.02	1.41 \pm 0.07	8.42 \pm 0.14
NBS 1412	7.52	4.67	4.14	7.50 \pm 0.13	4.65 \pm 0.08	4.16 \pm 0.09
NIST 1831	1.21	–	0.33	1.22 \pm 0.06	–	0.31 \pm 0.04
NIST 93a	2.28	–	0.014	2.30 \pm 0.07	–	0.016 \pm 0.005

^aMean of five replicates of observed value.**Table 5.** Results of base materials in neodymium doped phosphate glass samples using developed method

Glass samples	Observed result of elements oxide (w/w%) \pm SD		
	%Al ₂ O ₃	%BaO	%K ₂ O
Sample 1	6.48 \pm 0.22	11.54 \pm 0.25	11.52 \pm 0.29
Sample 2	6.53 \pm 0.19	12.30 \pm 0.23	11.52 \pm 0.19
Sample 3	6.64 \pm 0.21	11.22 \pm 0.24	11.21 \pm 0.24
Sample 4	5.92 \pm 0.15	11.12 \pm 0.18	10.64 \pm 0.18
Sample 5	6.57 \pm 0.23	11.26 \pm 0.24	11.79 \pm 0.22
Sample 6	6.65 \pm 0.17	13.02 \pm 0.25	11.94 \pm 0.30
Sample 7	6.72 \pm 0.20	11.70 \pm 0.19	11.77 \pm 0.19
Sample 8	6.59 \pm 0.16	12.85 \pm 0.15	11.89 \pm 0.25
Sample 9	6.69 \pm 0.18	13.04 \pm 0.20	12.01 \pm 0.22
Sample 10	6.70 \pm 0.20	12.45 \pm 0.18	12.15 \pm 0.28

was observed that the % (w/w) of Al₂O₃, BaO and K₂O was found in the range from 5.92% to 6.72%, 11.12% to 13.04% and 10.64% to 12.15% respectively. The analytical results of ten samples were presented in Table 5.

Conclusion

The developed method using ICP-AES is simple and precise for simultaneous determination of base materials in routine analysis of neodymium doped phosphate laser glass. It was shown that the significant effect of matrix did not observed on the performance of the proposed method. The accuracy of the method was studied by measuring recoveries at several metal concentrations in standard reference materials of different glass as well as in spiked solution and precision by % RSD. The developed

method was successfully employed in routine analysis of specialty glass like neodymium doped phosphate laser glass samples.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Professor Indranil Manna, Director, Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, Kolkata, India for his kind permission to submit this paper.

References

1. L. I. Avakyants, V. I. Molev, A. E. Pozdnyakov and V. F. Surkova, *Moscow Oblast Opticheski Zhurnal*, 2004, **71**, 32.
2. G. Karlsson, F. Laurell, J. Tellefsen, B. Denker, B. Galagan, V. Osiko and S. Sverchkov, *Appl. Phys. B : Lasers Opt.*, 2002, **75**, 41.
3. B. I. Galagan, I. K. Glushchenko, B. I. Denker, V. E. Kisel, S. V. Kurilchik, N. V. Kuleshov and S. E. Sverchkov, *Kvantovaya Elektron. (Moscow)*, 2009, **39**, 891 (*Quantum Electron. (Engl. transl.)*), 2009, **39**, 891.
4. R. Morena, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 2000, **263**, 382.
5. S. Matsumoto, N. Nakamura and N. Wada, WO 2009/088086 (09.01.2009).
6. N. Bahramifar and Y. Yamini, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **540**, 325.
7. N. Ytmes, S. Moyano, S. Cerutti, J. A. Gasquez and L. D. Martinez, *Talanta*, 2003, **59**, 943.
8. S. Cerutti, M. F. Silva, J. A. Gasquez, R. A. Olsina and L. D. Martinez, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B*, 2003, **58**, 43.
9. P. K. Sinha, S. Mandal, R. Samaddar and D. Kundu, *Glass Technology : European Journal of Glass Science and Technology Part A*, (in press).